

SUSTAINABILITY OF LOCAL ECONOMIC ENTERPRISES IN THE CITIES OF BATANGAS, LIPA AND TANAUAN: A PROPOSED MODEL FOR LOCAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

ROMANO M. BALBACAL

romano.balbacal@g.batstate-u.edu.ph

0000-0002-0817-203X

Lipa City Senior High School, Lipa City, Philippines

ABSTRACT

The term sustainable development originated from the United Nations World Commission on Environment and Development or the Brundtland Commission which means a development process that aims to meet the present demands while fostering the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. It promotes social development, which seeks cohesion and cultures to achieve satisfactory levels in quality of life, health, and education (World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987). It emphasizes equal economic growth that accumulates wealth for all with caring for the environment. The main objective of the study is to analyze the status, profile, level sustainability, challenges and problems encountered by the public enterprises in the Cities of Batangas, Lipa and Tanauan; with an endpoint of proposing a GROWTH Model for local economic development. This study is quantitative-qualitative study which employed mixed methods research that are combined with descriptive-correlational design with empirical surveys and interviews which involved documentary analyses for the collection of qualitative data to adequately address the research objectives. Generally, the status, profile and level of sustainability of Local Economic Enterprises in the three cities of Batangas have a great impact as agreed by the research participants. There is a significant relationship and difference in the status, profile and sustainability in the three cities of Batangas. Pandemic has a numerous adverse effect in the status and profile of the public enterprises. Attitudinal problems of the employees slightly affect the quality-of-service delivery of LEEs in the component cities of Batangas. Sustainability of LEEs in the component cities of Batangas hinge on their income stability, plans for their future expansion, and operational continuity completely portrayed as high extent. The proposed GROWTH Model maybe evaluated for the integration of the local economic development plan in the component cities of Batangas.

Keywords: Public Administration, local economic enterprise, sustainability, Philippines